

[Shaye Hirsch](#) is a painter, born in 1956 in Brooklyn, New York. He studied at the New York University and hold a Bachelor of Art Degree in Fine Arts.

In Hirsch canvases there are references to great masters such as Duchamp and Picasso, using a special subjectivity in the treatment of color. At the same time, there are, in an ironic and sarcastic way, constant references to the great artistic and literary movements of the 20th century and an acid social criticism.

The colorism of Pop Art has greatly influenced some of the paintings of Hirsch, who also moves away from realistic figuration and embraces the graphic and varied world of modern art.

[All the elements that make up his paintings](#), whether they are appropriations or not, resonate as indispensable parts of Hirsch relationship with the outside. He has established this relationship with a marked humorous, playful and ironic accent.

In all of his paintings, Hirsch makes a subjective treatment of color that alludes to the artistic and literary movements of the 20th century, using irony and making a social criticism. Hence, everything he captures in his paintings are essential parts of his relationship with the world, this being of a humorous nature.

[The artworks](#) of Shaye Hirsch are colorful, lively, and abstract, but quite coherent and direct in its message.

The painter has been exhibiting at various galleries, since 1985 and has collaborated for years with the New York Art Gallery.